

TABLE-1 (ALL WEIGHTS REPORTED HERE ARE IN MG)

Sl. No.	Estimation of X as [Y L Ni X]	Metal X taken	Y=en			Y=DAP			Y=DAMP		
			Weight of complex	X found	Error	Weight of complex	X found	Error	Weight complex	X found	Error
1.	Mg as [Y L Ni Mg]	30	539.0	30.1	+0.10	553.2	29.92	-0.08	573.3	30.08	+0.08
		40	727.1	40.06	+0.06	739.6	40.00	0.00	760.5	39.90	-0.10
		50	895.8	50.02	+0.02	924.7	50.01	+0.01	954.9	50.10	+0.10
2.	Ca as [Y L Ni Ca]	30	338.5	30.06	+0.06	347.6	29.94	-0.06	359.4	30.05	+0.05
		40	450.5	40.01	+0.01	463.4	39.91	-0.09	479.6	40.10	+0.10
		50	562.4	49.95	-0.05	580.73	50.02	+0.02	598.9	50.08	+0.08
3.	Sr as [Y L Ni Sr]	30	171.2	30.08	+0.08	176.1	30.09	+0.09	180.5	30.02	+0.02
		40	227.6	39.99	-0.01	234.7	40.10	+0.10	240.1	40.05	+0.05
		50	284.3	49.96	-0.04	292.6	50.00	0.00	300.8	50.03	+0.03
4.	Ba as [Y L Ni Ba]	30	120.5	29.90	-0.10	122.1	29.93	-0.07	126.0	30.00	0.00
		40	159.4	39.89	-0.11	163.5	39.90	-0.10	167.7	39.94	-0.06
		50	199.4	49.91	-0.09	204.6	49.95	-0.05	210.0	50.01	+0.01

Results and Discussion

Analytical data in Table 1 show that the metal complex i.e. Na₂ Ni complexes can be used for the gravimetric estimation of magnesium, calcium, strontium and barium. Solutions containing as little as 10 mg can be determined by this method. Common anions like chloride, bromide, nitrate etc. do not interfere in the determination of the coloured complexes [YL Ni Mg], [Y L Ni Ca], [Y L Ni Sr] and [Y L Ni Ba]. The complexes are stable upto 250°, above this temperature they start decomposing. Only the MgNi complexes are soluble in methyl alcohol. The remaining are insoluble in water, acetone, alcohol, chloroform, carbon tetrachloride, ether, benzene and pyridine.

Acknowledgement

The author is grateful to the University Grants Commission for awarding him the Colombo Plan Fellowship to attend the Unesco course on Research Techniques in Chemistry at the School of Chemistry, University of New South Wales, Australia, where most of this work was carried out.

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H₂O₂-Extinction Coefficients of Homoionic Soils (Na-, K-, NH₄- and H-soils) in Aqueous Media at Different Temperatures

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Manuscript received 20 March 1975, revised 1 November 1975;
accepted 5 January 1976

THE study of H₂O₂ decomposition by different homoionic soils (particularly of U. P., India) appears to have not been done, although works are available to show the effect of different salts, pH, organic

fertilizers and mild acids on soil catalase activity¹. Here, attempts have been made to show the extent of H₂O₂ decomposition by a few samples of U. P. soils saturated with Na⁺, K⁺, NH₄⁺ and H⁺ ions.

Eleven U. P. soils (0-6") belonging to different soil-climatic regions were collected and H₂O₂-extinction coefficients (K) of their monovalent homoionic forms (Na-, K-, NH₄- and H-soils) were determined in aqueous media at 20°, 30° and 40°.

To make these soil samples homoionic with respect to H-, Na-, NH₄-, and K-ions, they were treated with N-HCl, N-NaCl, N-NH₄Cl and N-KCl solutions (1 : 10) respectively and shaken well. After 24 hr, the soil suspensions were filtered through Buchner funnel and leached four times with the same solutions. Finally, the samples left on the filter paper were then removed, dried, powdered and passed through 100-mesh sieve, for subsequent work.

For the estimation of H₂O₂ decomposition, 2.0 g. of each soil sample was taken in 100 ml. measuring flask and volume was made up with 0.1 N H₂O₂ solution. The flasks were then kept in a thermostat at 20°, 30° and 40°. From each flask, 20.0 ml. aliquots were taken out after 5, 15, 30 and 60 min. and were centrifuged to get a clear solution and from this solution H₂O₂ decomposition was estimated iodometrically². A blank experiment was also carried out. K value was calculated from the first order equation of kinetics as follows :

$$K = \frac{2.303}{t} \log_{10} \frac{a}{a-x}$$

where, K = H₂O₂ - extinction coefficients, a = initial concentration of H₂O₂, x = quantity of H₂O₂ decomposed, and t = time of reaction.

A perusal of Table 1 would clearly show that the K values recorded at 5, 15, 30 and 60 mts. did not give constant values and, therefore, did not obey first order reaction equation. This was expected because of the heterogenous nature of soil. Pure H₂O₂ solution in pure catalase will, however, follow first order equation

NOTES

of kinetics. Thus, in soils it is not only soil catalase but a number of other factors that are also operating and influencing the H₂O₂ - decomposition in aqueous media.

comparing the different K values, it may be observed that the saturating cations show different K-values as shown below :

TABLE 1
MEAN H₂O₂-EXTINCTION COEFFICIENTS OF SOILS IN AQUEOUS MEDIA AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES

Temp. (°C)	H ₂ O ₂ -Extinction coefficients'										$\frac{K \times 10^{-3}}{4} \text{ min}^{-1}$
	Jaunpur (SL)	Ghazipur (SL)	Banda (C)	Jhansi (SL)	Allahabad (CL)	Fatehpur (SCL)	Agra (SL)	Aligarh (SL)	Gorakhpur (SL)	Nainital (SL)	
<i>Na-soils :</i>											
20	7.050	6.807	4.210	2.583	9.902	9.694	7.350	5.549	4.113	3.425	2.239
30	4.383	6.020	4.055	2.108	9.683	8.015	5.118	3.633	4.002	2.868	2.002
40	8.262	11.902	7.655	5.318	18.915	12.850	8.544	6.348	6.511	4.500	2.445
<i>K-soils :</i>											
20	NR	6.188	5.144	1.586	5.992	5.352	5.652	3.709	3.632	3.118	3.709
30	0.830	4.220	4.122	2.145	6.618	9.224	5.133	3.020	2.563	2.187	1.508
40	0.292	7.354	6.701	3.278	11.612	7.371	7.853	4.322	5.496	3.754	3.082
<i>NH₄-soils :</i>											
20	1.029	1.281	4.665	0.943	3.162	1.870	1.949	1.032	1.241	0.290	0.794
30	0.660	1.077	2.902	0.305	2.754	1.569	1.756	0.732	1.370	0.128	0.561
40	1.160	2.440	6.124	1.269	4.974	2.860	3.113	1.197	3.226	0.867	0.926
<i>H-soils :</i>											
20	NR	NR	0.156	0.009	0.183	0.147	0.018	0.018	0.509	0.131	0.025
30	0.024	0.024	0.469	0.099	0.472	0.289	0.048	0.340	0.763	0.095	0.127
40	0.191	0.260	0.970	0.238	0.658	1.019	0.376	0.139	1.376	0.237	0.369

Note : NR = No reaction, SL = Sandy loam, C = Clay, CL = Clay loam, SCL = Sandy clay loam, LS = Loamy sand

Clay loam, Allahabad and sandy clay loam, Fatehpur soils record maximum K values as far as the K values of Na-soil concerned. The loamy sand, Almora and sandy loam, Nainital or Jhansi soils, however, record the lowest values of K (Table 1). In case of K-soil, sandy loam, Ghazipur and clay loam, Allahabad recorded the maximum K values at 20°. At 30° and 40°, clay loam, Allahabad recorded maximum H₂O₂ decomposition with K-soils. Generally, at all the three temperatures, clayey-Banda and clay loam, Allahabad soils have been found to record maximum K values and sandy loam, Nainital gave the lowest (Table 1). In case of H-soils, sandy loam, Gorakhpur recorded the maximum K values followed by clay loam, Allahabad or sandy clay loam, Fatehpur soils whereas sandy loam, Ghazipur, Jaunpur or Aligarh recorded the lowest K values. In case of NH₄ soils, clayey-Banda soil followed by clay loam, Allahabad gave highest decomposition of H₂O₂ and the sandy loam, Nainital followed by loamy sand, Almora or sandy loam. Jhansi have given the lowest. However, it appears to be generally true that irrespective of cation saturation the catalytic activity on H₂O₂ decreases as the texture of the soil varies from clay loam to sandy loam (Table 1).

The efficiency order of temperatures would show that for each soil there is a temperature specificity for the reaction in relation to its predominant cations. For Na-, K-, NH₄⁻ and H-soils, H₂O₂ decomposition is maximum at 40°. For Na- and NH₄⁻ soils, the minimum K values are at 30°. For K- and H- soils, the minimum generally appeared to be at 30°. On

Galstyan also pointed out that Na⁺ rich soils had high catalytic activity (in terms of high H₂O₂-decomposition).

It may be pointed out here that H₂O₂ catalytic reaction is a reduction process and occurs more under alkaline conditions according to the following equation :

It, therefore, appears that on the saturation of soil with H⁺, this reduction process will be lessened than what will take place in presence of Na⁺ or other saturating cations. The soil conditions (higher pH; clay loam and sandy clay loam, 30°) under which higher K-values had been obtained are, therefore, not suitable for H₂O₂ accumulation which might have proved toxic to plants.

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